

Access to Context: Data-Envelopes for Digital Cultural Heritage in Practice

Maria Eskevich^{1,4}, Sebastiaan Derks^{1,5}, Juliette Huygen^{1,6},
Roeland Ordelman^{2,7}, Niek Verhoeff^{3,8}, and Mari Wigham^{1,9}

¹Huygens Instituut, KNAW

²Het Nederlands Instituut voor Beeld en Geluid

³Het Stadsarchief Amsterdam

⁴ORCID: 0000-0002-1242-0753

⁵ORCID: 0000-0002-1255-5324

⁶ORCID: 0009-0008-2359-3503

⁷ORCID: 0000-0001-9229-0006

⁸ORCID: 0000-0002-9968-9535

⁹ORCID: 0000-0002-2784-1921

In the humanities and heritage sector, many datasets are becoming available for research and interdisciplinary use, partly due to data-driven innovations and new digitisation technologies. At the same time, digital processing of data on cultural assets is not documented in a comparable way in most projects, and most current metadata models and various dataset registries do not provide enough space for adequate description¹. Addressing this problem requires consensus and support for an overarching descriptive model for dataset disclosure that follows Open Science practices and facilitates data discovery, sharing and reuse.

In the field of machine learning there is a trend to use so-called datasheets that map the characteristics of a data object, dataset or software system to add context and summarise technical and commercial information in particular(1). Analysis and experiments at the Huygens Institute in conversation with other partners in the field have shown that these versions of datasheets are not sufficient to properly express the complexity and heterogeneity of the cultural heritage data. This led to the introduction of the new concept of data-envelopes(2) which specifically gives space to information that is important for this very field; for researchers, the wider public as well as for machines. This description model offers the possibility of achieving a balance in dataset descriptions where important cultural information can be described in detail across different types of facets by researchers and other dataset creators. For example, the data-envelopes also incorporate information on provenance (in what context these sources were created), context around FAIR principles (e.g. where can the data be found and in what format; what does someone need to know before they reuse

¹ See for example datasets register from Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed, NDE, (<https://datasetregister.netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/>) and datasets and tools catalogue INEO (<https://www.ineo.tools/>)

Figure 1: Project activities overview.

the dataset) and positionality (who worked on it and what does that possibly say about bias and blind spots). Moreover, the data-envelopes (in addition to the other datasheets) add facets that are actually machine-readable, and therefore, enhance interoperability with other systems and findability.

The project 'Toegang tot context: Data-envelopes voor digitaal cultureel erfgoed in de praktijk' (*Access to Context: Data-envelopes for Digital Cultural Heritage in Practice*) carried out by three institutions (Huygens Institute², the Stadsarchief Amsterdam³ and the Nederlands Instituut voor Beeld en Geluid⁴) from December 2024 till December 2025 has two objectives. On the one hand, we test the applicability of data-envelopes for other types of data (e.g. audiovisual data and administrative datasets); on the other hand, we identify technical requirements for preserving and sharing data envelopes (within the organisations and) via external catalogues, such as INEO, CLARIAH⁵, SSH Open Market Place⁶, EUROPEANA⁷, NDE⁸ en E-RIHS⁹. These activities will result in a data-envelopes proof-of-concept and implementation plan for further application and use in the field. Figure 1 provides an overview of project activities omitting administrative activities 1 and 8, and focusing on the content ones.

At DH Benelux 2025 we present the project midterm achievements, and use the discussions as input for the implementation and dissemination strategy of data-envelopes use beyond the project timeline.

References

- [1] Timnit Gebru, Jamie Morgenstern, Briana Vecchione, Jennifer Wortman Vaughan, Hanna Wallach, Hal Daumé Iii, and Kate Crawford. Datasheets for datasets. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(12):86–92, 2021.
- [2] Mrinalini Luthra and Maria Eskevich. Data-envelopes for cultural heritage: Going beyond datasheets. In Ingo Siegert and Khalid Choukri, editors, *Proceedings of the Workshop on Legal and Ethical Issues in Human Language Technologies @ LREC-COLING 2024*, pages 52–65, Torino, Italia, May 2024. ELRA and ICCL.

² <https://www.huygens.knaw.nl>
³ <https://www.amsterdam.nl/stadsarchief/>
⁴ <https://www.beeldengeluid.nl>
⁵ <https://www.clariah.nl>
⁶ <https://sshopencloud.eu/ssh-open-marketplace>
⁷ <https://www.europeana.eu/nl>
⁸ <https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl>
⁹ <https://e-rihs.nl>